

Sikh Formations

Religion, Culture, Theory

ISSN: 1744-8727 (Print) 1744-8735 (Online) Journal homepage: www.tandfonline.com/journals/rsfo20

'I have seen all places, but none can compare to you': Classifying *gurdwara* architecture in the Sikh diaspora

Silvia Omenetto

To cite this article: Silvia Omenetto (13 May 2026): 'I have seen all places, but none can compare to you': Classifying *gurdwara* architecture in the Sikh diaspora, Sikh Formations, DOI: [10.1080/17448727.2026.2660044](https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2026.2660044)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2026.2660044>

© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

Published online: 13 May 2026.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 88

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

'I have seen all places, but none can compare to you': Classifying *gurdwara* architecture in the Sikh diaspora

Silvia Omenetto

Department of Storia, Antropologia, Religioni, Arte e Spettacolo, Università di Roma, Rome, Italy

ABSTRACT

While Sikh diaspora studies are extensive, architectural variations of *gurdwaras* remain underexamined. This article addresses this gap by extending Myrvold's (2007) taxonomy through the integration of 'iconicity' and 'iconic aspiration' with the geographical concept of 'infrasecular spaces.' I propose a tripartite framework: Iconic *gurdwaras*, replicating traditional Punjabi forms; Iconic aspiration *gurdwaras*, adapting traditional motifs to local urban constraints; and Infrasecular *gurdwaras*, occupying repurposed buildings. This typology analyzes the nexus between social function and material form, offering a versatile tool for examining architectural evolution across diverse diasporic religious landscapes.

KEYWORDS

Sikh diaspora; *gurdwara*; architecture; iconicity; infrasecular space; Singapore; Italy

Introduction

At the entrance of the *Gurdwara Sahib* in Yishun in Singapore, an image of the *Harmandir Sahib* in Amritsar welcomes visitors and devotees with an English caption: *I have seen all places, but none can compare to you*. The reference to the Golden Temple, central to Sikhs worldwide, is here made explicit in an imposing visual and textual form, differing from other *gurdwaras* where the *Harmandir Sahib* – also known as Golden Temple – typically appears discreetly, often confined to a framed painting on the wall, positioned beside the representations of the Ten Gurus.

Positioned in a liminal but not marginal location – on the temple's entrance threshold – the image does more than evoke a distant sacred site: it shapes the spatial experience of the local *gurdwara*, symbolically inscribing it within a transnational religious geography (Figure 1).

The observed visual device highlights a persistent tension in *gurdwaras* of the Sikh diaspora,¹ between the desire to maintain symbolic continuity with a shared sacred center and the need to adapt to local contexts. In this regard, the Golden Temple plays a central role: as Kirti Nishant Nikam notes, 'Many *Gurdwaras* now incorporate design elements that reflect the pattern of *Harmandir Sahib*, the holiest Sikh shrine in Amritsar' (2024, 16). Its influence extends beyond the theological and historical model (Kaur 2023),

CONTACT Silvia Omenetto silvia.omenetto@uniroma1.it

This article has been corrected with minor changes. These changes do not impact the academic content of the article.

© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

Figure 1. Poster placed at the entrance of the Gurdwara Sahib in Yishun, Singapore, 9 November 2025. Source: Author.

shaping both the aesthetics and materiality, as well as the architecture and spatial organization of *gurdwaras* in the world.

At the same time, *gurdwaras* reflect adaptation to new contexts: they can be considered *sites of transnational influences and practices that are accommodated in new local settings* (Myrvold and Jacobsen 2011, 8), where architectural forms and building materials interact with fundamental Sikh principles, such as equality and service (Nikam 2024). Spatial configurations result from complex negotiations with urban, economic, and regulatory constraints, aspects that have received limited attention so far. Despite a consolidated body of research on the Sikh diaspora (Axel 2001; Barrier and Dusenbery 1989; Hawley 2013), architectural variations among *gurdwaras* remain underexplored, and there is a lack of systematic analysis relating them to these structural factors.

This article seeks to address this gap by extending Kristina Myrvold's (2007) socio-historical classification of *gurdwaras* to their geographic and architectural dimensions in diasporic contexts. The analysis integrates the concepts of *iconicity* and *iconic aspiration*, emerging from the spatial and material turn in Religious Studies, with the concept of *infrasecular spaces* developed in *Geography of Religions* (Beekers and Tamimi Arab 2016; della Dora 2018, 2025; Knott, Krech, and Meyer 2016).

Three categories of diasporic *gurdwaras* are distinguished based on architectural and material characteristics. 'Iconic' *gurdwaras* replicate the architectural and aesthetic features of traditional Sikh temples, explicitly referencing formal models associated with the Harmandir Sahib and other historic sites in Punjab. 'Iconic aspiration' *gurdwaras*

similarly draw on traditional forms but adapt them to the functional, economic, and contextual conditions of Italian urban and peri-urban settings. By contrast, ‘infrasecular’ *gurdwaras* occupy repurposed buildings – such as homes, warehouses, or workshops – producing hybrid forms shaped by local materials, regulations, and resources.

Singapore, as a city–state, and Italy, as a national context, offer a privileged vantage point for testing this distinction, as both represent fully diasporic settings while revealing different modes of negotiation between symbolic continuity and local constraints. In Singapore, the Sikh presence is historically established, with approximately 12,500 people officially classified as part of the ‘Indian’ group (Department of Statistics Singapore 2021; Kaur 2021; Singh 2023; Woods and Kong 2022, 2024). The seven existing *gurdwaras* are embedded in a dense and regulated urban fabric, often designed or adapted in buildings that reference traditional architectural forms while responding to urban and regulatory constraints. In Italy, by contrast, the Sikh community is more recent (Bertolani 2015, 2018), numbering around 88,700 people (Zanfrini 2024). *Gurdwaras* frequently emerge through the reuse of pre-existing buildings in peri-urban or rural contexts, giving rise to hybrid configurations adapted to local materials and available economic resources (Omenetto 2015).

Building on a mixed-methods approach, this article adopts an analytical comparative perspective rather than a scalar one. Singapore and Italy are examined not as equivalent political units, but as contrasting diasporic contexts in which Sikh communities negotiate architectural form, materiality, and public visibility under distinct regulatory and urban regimes. This approach follows methodological insights on comparative research in urban studies, religious studies, and socio-spatial analysis (Freiberger 2019; Le Galès and Robinson 2024; Robinson 2022).

This comparative distinction, combined with the classification of *gurdwaras* into ‘iconicity’, ‘iconic aspiration’, and ‘infrasecular’ types, provides analytical tools to explore how *gurdwaras* adapt across established and migratory settings, highlighting the coexistence of tradition and innovation within the Sikh diaspora.

The article is structured as follows. Section 1 provides a review of the literature on Sikh Diaspora Studies, with a particular focus on *gurdwara* architecture, situating the analytical categories employed in this study within recent debates in Religious Studies and the Geography of Religions. Section 2 focuses on the classification of *gurdwaras*, referring to Myrvold’s (2007) taxonomy. Section 3 describes the methodology, based on direct observation, interviews, and visual research. Section 4 analyses the *gurdwaras* of Singapore, considering their historical and regulatory context, as well as their contemporary forms and materialities. Section 5 explores Italian *gurdwaras*, reconstructing their founding and spread across the national territory, the factors shaping their materiality and location, and the main architectural typologies. Finally, the conclusion frames the classification as a lens to examine the interplay of social, symbolic, and architectural elements, serving as flexible comparative categories.

Gurdwaras and architecture: analytical framework

Literature review

Sikhs have long been described as a ‘people on the move’ (Talbot and Thandi 2004 in Jacobsen and Myrvold 2012, 1; Tatla 1999). The literature on the Sikh diaspora has

explored multiple dimensions of the global dispersion of Punjabi Sikh communities. It shows how these communities articulate memory, citizenship, and political participation, reflect on multicultural dynamics and gender issues, express themselves through literature, oral history, and musical practices, and regulate economic and marital relationships while living the beliefs and rituals of Sikhism in everyday life, including respect for and care of the environment (Hawley 2013; Kaur 2020; Singh and Fenech 2014; Takhar and Jakobsh 2023).

However, although these studies offer significant insights into multiple aspects, Sikh geography in the diaspora remains relatively under-researched (Kaur 2016), and within it, architecture – understood as the material and situated expression of space – has largely remained marginal (Kaur 2023). Knut A. Jacobsen notes that ‘in published volumes on Sikh identity and the Sikh diaspora, studies on *gurdwaras* are often surprisingly non-existent’, probably because – as he himself observes – many researchers in Sikh studies are primarily historians and textual scholars (2012, 107).

Pioneering studies on the topic have not been lacking (Arshi 1986; Bhatti 1987; Cole 1973; Singh 1998). Although numerous publications have analyzed Sikh religious space – from its evolution from the *dharamsāls*, to Islamic and Hindu architectural influences, to material aspects – many works have focused on the five *takht* (*Pañj Takhat*), the so-called ‘five thrones,’ and on buildings constructed between the sixteenth and nineteenth centuries in India and Pakistan (Ghada 2021; Glover 2012; Kaur 2021, 2023; Malhotra 2023; Karamjit Singh Chahal 2012).

Among Sikh architectures, the Harmandir Sahib occupies a central role due to its historical and religious significance (Kaur 2023, 641), influencing a substantial body of research that has studied its geometry to understand philosophical and spatial relationships, or its architectural evolution (Dokras 2021; Kaur 1983; Kaur 2023; Kochhar 2020; Singh and Singh Chahal 2014). Other studies have analyzed the pedestrian paths leading to the Temple, contributing to the definition of its sacredness (Singh, Kaur, and Kaur 2017). Finally, more recent research has examined the potential of architectural elements and spaces as guiding forces in shaping spiritual experiences (Kaur 2025).

In this context, studies on architectural variations appear to occupy a marginal space. When temples in the diaspora are the subject of specific research – as Gurhpal Singh and Darshan Singh Tatla (2006, 5) point out – the focus is on management or conflicts (2006, 69–93; Sian 2012) and – geographically – on the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom (Dhesi 2009; Hirvi 2014; Peach and Gale 2003; Singh 2006; Singh and Baniwal 2024; Stoker 2013; Townsend 2018).

The term *gurdwara* does not appear trivially in the name index of some handbooks on Sikhism outside India (Singh and Fenech 2014). In most published texts, only five references are present. One chapter was written by Knut A. Jacobsen in the volume *Sikhs Across Borders. Transnational Practices of European Sikhs*, also edited by Jacobsen together with Jacobsen and Myrvold (2012). The author provides a brief overview of academic studies on temples, the history of their construction in Europe, and some devotional practices carried out in *gurdwaras* (e.g. Kirtan). Another reference to a temple in Quebec (Canada) is found in the chapter written by Valerie Stoker in the volume *Sikh Diaspora: Theory, Agency, and Experience*, edited by Michael Hawley (2013). A study on the role and functions of *gurdwaras* in British Columbia as central sites for creating Sikh identity, community, and sacred space, reflecting core Sikh principles

such as equality and service in diasporic contexts, was conducted by Kamala Elizabeth Nayar (2010).

More recently, the volume *Sikhs in Continental Europe. From Norway to Greece and Russia to Portugal*, edited in 2021 by Swarn Singh Kahlon (2021), dedicated its eighteenth chapter to temples. In six pages, it attempts to trace the chronology of the foundations of Sikh temples outside Punjab, listing in particular the temples in Germany and Italy, 40 and 30 respectively. While the figure for Germany seems correct, the one for Italy is not up to date (Omenetto 2015). Finally, a chapter published in the volume *The Sikh World*, edited by Pashaura Singh and Arvind-Pal Singh Mandair, is also noteworthy. In this book, Tejpal Singh Bainiwal Singh (2023) dedicates his chapter to the history and evolution of the *gurdwara*, the daily routines within a Sikh temple, its role in a Sikh's life, and the various types of *gurdwaras*.

This section concludes on a positive note. Recent studies have indeed begun to link Sikh migration, *gurdwaras*, and architectural evolution, highlighting the aesthetic and structural variations of religious sites both in India and in more distant contexts. Starting from the religious heart of Sikhism, Nikam (2024) explores themes of religious philosophy and human consciousness through architecture, focusing on the evolution of *gurdwaras*. The study begins with the analysis of the Golden Temple and extends to modern buildings such as Sheeshe Wala Gurudwara in Meerut Cantt (Uttar Pradesh), Gurdwara Hemkunt Sahib in the Himalayas, Chamoli (Uttarakhand), and Sri Guru Singh Sabha Gurdwara in Gurugram (Haryana).

Bhonsle, Kaur, and Nikam (2023) expand the analysis by comparing historic, contemporary, and newly designed *gurdwaras* in contexts both near and farther from India. Case studies include Gurdwara Guru Nanak Darbar in Dubai (United Arab Emirates) and Gurudwara Shri Kalgidhar Sahib in Takanini (New Zealand). In these examples, traditional architecture is reinterpreted in a modern key, adapting to local materials and needs.

Moving to major Western diaspora destinations, Brar, Dhanjal, and Scott (2021) analyse the link between Sikh migration in Canada and the architectural evolution of temples along the West Coast, comparing historic and modern buildings. Among the former, the Sikh Temple in Abbotsford (1911), now a National Historic Site of Canada, recalls the wooden houses of frontier villages while incorporating traditional Sikh elements, especially in the interiors. Among the latter, the Gurdwara of the Khalsa Diwan Society in Vancouver, built in 1970, represents a fusion of Western modernism and Sikh symbolism. The structure develops over five reinforced concrete levels, with the upper three rotated 45°, and a central cube with a domed skylight. Reinterpreted traditional details, such as gilded domes, geometric symmetry, and the *nishan sahib* at the entrance, complete the ensemble.

As a complement to the above studies, Barbara Bertolani (2020) studied the *gurdwaras* of Southall in West London (UK), adopting a sociological approach rather than the geographic or architectural perspective of the previously cited studies. Her research focuses on community dynamics, religious practices, and the social role of these spaces in the Sikh diaspora. Although not the primary aim of the study, Bertolani considers certain spatial and architectural features – such as building size, property type, exterior recognizability, and accessibility – as contextualization tools useful for understanding the organization and use of spaces by the London Sikh community.

Architecture, iconicity and infrasecular religious space

Research on Sikh architecture remains limited, and Sikhism itself is often underrepresented in the broader field of Religious Studies (Jacobsen 2012). In contrast, religious architecture more generally is a well established topic, as demonstrated by studies on as shown by studies on mosques, Christian churches, Hindu and Buddhist temples mosques, Romanian Orthodox church and Pentecostal buildings (Beaumont 2010; Beekers and Tamimi Arab 2016; Burchardt et al. 2023; Cozma et al. 2023; Giorda 2024; Katsaura 2023; Koch, Valiyev, and Hazmi Zaini 2018).

Over the past twenty years, the humanities and social sciences have introduced new ways of conceptualizing space, place, and landscape as active and performative entities (Lefebvre 1991; Soja 1996), with significant implications for the study of religion (Knott 2005), which I consider useful for the study of Sikh spatiality. Alongside the ‘spatial turn’ (Knott 2010; Obadia 2015), the so-called ‘material turn’ has highlighted how religion manifests through objects, bodies, images, media, and spaces (Meyer and Moors 2003; Vásquez 2011). Materiality should not be seen as a mere container of pre-given meanings, but as an active factor in the production of religious meaning, capable of influencing believers’ perceptions, experiences, and practices (Hazard 2019; Houtman and Meyer 2012; Morgan 2021; Tamimi Arab, Hughes, and Brent Rodríguez-Plate 2024). In this sense, materiality is not merely a matter of aesthetics or outward appearance; rather, as Anne Murphy (2012) convincingly argues, it is a primary vehicle through which the Sikh tradition represents and renders the past present in the contemporary world. Material objects and architectural forms do not just ‘symbolize’ history; they perform it, creating a tangible continuity between the Guru’s era and the lived experience of the diaspora.

In particular, religious architecture assumes a central function: it does not only represent the physical space in which religion is practiced but also constitutes a symbolic and political medium within the city. Sacred buildings shape collective imagination, define inclusion and exclusion, and establish the visibility and legitimacy of religious communities (de Wildt et al. 2019; Verkaaik 2013). As visual markers of religious presence, they contribute to constructing social perception of the community and influence its representation in urban space, recording dynamics of inclusion, exclusion, and power relations (Knowles 2013).

A particularly relevant theoretical concept for this analysis is that of ‘iconic religion,’ developed by Knott, Krech, and Meyer (2016). From this perspective, religions become visible and interpretable in the public domain through objects, images, architecture, and ritual practices. In highly mediated and visual contexts, religious visibility manifests primarily through iconic forms: elements that convey religious meaning in an immediately recognizable way, circulating through urban space and helping shape collective imagination, as in the case of the *gurdwaras* in Singapore.

Unlike the traditional symbolic approach, which interprets symbols as references to hidden or transcendent meanings, ‘iconicity’ focuses on the visual and material impact of religious representations (Bartmański and Alexander 2012). Icons do not merely represent the sacred but make it present in urban space, generating recognition, familiarity, suspicion, or conflict. The concept implies a direct correspondence between sign and referent: for example, a minaret evokes Islam, a cross evokes Christianity.

From the concept of ‘iconic religion’ derives the idea of ‘iconic aspiration,’ developed by Beekers and Tamimi Arab (2016), which describes the explicit or implicit desire of many religious communities – often minorities – to make their presence visible in public space through buildings that are easily recognizable and rich in symbolic meaning (Burchardt and Westendorp 2018). ‘Iconic aspiration’ implies the intention to design places of worship that are not only functional but also convey aesthetic and identity values, becoming genuine visual signals of religion within the city. These ambitions, however, often face regulatory constraints, political obstacles, or economic limits, complicating their practical realization.

Geography of Religion has also contributed to the debate and attention on religious spatialities and architectures (Kong, Woods, and Tse 2025). Since the 1990s, this field has gradually moved away from static and binary conceptions of spatial configurations, adopting more dynamic and fluid approaches that investigate the fragile boundary between sacred and profane in urban environments (Cloke and Johnston 2005; Finlayson 2017; Richardson 2022; Tse 2014). A key contribution in this sense was Lily Kong’s (2001) invitation to look beyond the official and visible forms of religious space, paving the way for critical reflections on processes of reuse, conversion, and the multiple spatialities of urban religion (Gökarıksel 2009; Hackworth and Gullikson 2013; Lynch 2016; Lynch and LeDrew 2022; Stephenson and Lynch 2025; Wigley 2018; Woods 2012). In this framework, the concept of ‘infrasecular space’, developed by Veronica della Dora (2018), proves particularly useful for analyzing the materiality of the ‘grey zone’ generated by the interaction between religious and secular aesthetic elements, as in Italian *gurdwaras*. Drawing on concepts such as Soja’s (1996) third space, Massey’s (1993) geometries of power, and Perec’s (1974) infra-ordinary, the infrasecular emphasizes coexistence, overlap, and transformation, showing how religion can be shaped, reinterpreted, or masked in hybrid configurations. Empirical studies highlight the fluidity of sacred landscapes and the porosity of boundaries between religious and secular, visible and invisible, institutional and informal (Dempsey 2023; Jordan 2022; Platt, Abushena, and Snape 2021).

Classifying *gurdwaras*: historical and diasporic perspectives

Without aiming to provide a comprehensive historical and etymological reconstruction of the term ‘gurdwara’, which has already been widely discussed in the literature (Malhotra 2023; Singha 2000, 86), it is useful to recall some basic information before analyzing the main classifications of Sikh temple. The term *gurdwara* derives from the Punjabi words *guru* (spiritual guide) and *dwara* (door), literally meaning ‘the Guru’s door.’ Originally, Sikhs gathered in *dharamsāls* to practice the teachings of Guru Nanak Dev Ji and the subsequent ten Gurus (Bainiwal Singh 2023; Kaur 2023). Over time, the *gurdwara* evolved into a formal institution capable of materializing and spatializing the three fundamental principles of Sikhism (Nayar 2010): remembering God, leading an honest life, and sharing with others. These principles are embodied respectively in the *darbar hall*, where the *Sri Guru Granth Sahib* – the holy text and the living guru – is kept during the day and moved to the *sach khand* at night; in the *sewa*, or voluntary service for the care and daily management of the *gurdwara*; and in the *langar*, the communal kitchen (Bhonsle, Kaur, and Nikam 2023).

The evolution of the *gurdwara*'s functions has followed different trajectories over time, reflecting not only the core principles of Sikhism but also the specificities of the migratory histories of Sikh communities (Ballantyne 2006). This diversification has necessitated the development of interpretive tools capable of capturing differences across temples. Within this framework, Kristina Myrvold proposed a first socio-historical classification distinguishing between 'historic *gurdwaras*' and 'diasporic *gurdwaras*' (2007, 154–156).

'Historic *gurdwaras*' are primarily located in India, Pakistan, and Afghanistan. Their foundations are closely tied to Sikh history and include places of birth and death of the Gurus, sites associated with the founding of the *Khalsa* – the congregation – and locations linked to the martyrdom of notable Sikhs. Among these are the five *takhts* – *Pañj Takhat*, or 'five thrones' – temples of great importance to the Sikh community, all located in modern-day India.

The literature identifies architectural elements in historic *gurdwaras* dating back to the fourteenth century, consolidated by Guru Ram Das Ji and Guru Arjan Dev Ji during the construction of the first Harmandir Sahib. These elements evolved over time, integrating Mughal stylistic influences – evident in onion domes, frescoes, and stepped arches – and Rajput influences, recognizable in *chhatris*, projecting balconies, brackets, and decorated portals (Bhui 1999; Nikam 2024).

Most Sikh temples located outside the original geographic area of Sikhism, including all *gurdwaras* in Western contexts, fall into the category of 'diasporic *gurdwaras*' identified by Myrvold (2007). This definition refers to public spaces dedicated to collective practice and the social and religious sharing of Sikhs. The literature identifies three main phases in the Punjabi diaspora (Garha and Valls 2017), each influencing the spread and foundation of *gurdwaras* abroad. The first phase, during the colonial period (1860–1947), saw Sikhs move along British Empire routes to Canada, the United States, East Africa, Southeast Asia – including Fiji, Singapore, Malaysia, Hong Kong, and China – and Oceania. The second phase occurred in the post-colonial period: following the partition of Punjab in 1947 and the intercommunal violence that ensued, many Sikhs migrated to the United Kingdom; from the 1970s onward, migration restrictions in some European countries encouraged further movements to the Gulf monarchies, attracted by opportunities generated by the oil boom (Bharadwaj, Khwaja, and Mian 2008). The third phase, beginning in 1984 with Operation Blue Star and subsequent anti-Sikh violence in India, led to new migratory flows to North America, Europe, and emerging destinations, including Italy (Garha and Valls 2017).

These *gurdwaras*, established to meet the religious needs of migrant communities, have played a central role from the outset as sites of social support, providing meals, housing, and assistance. Over time, some have acquired significant importance, consolidating their centrality within the diaspora. Myrvold identifies an exemplary subgroup represented, for instance, by the first *gurdwaras* founded in Canada and the United States, whose historical development reinforced their role as reference points for the global Sikh community (Brar, Dhanjal, and Scott 2021).

Based on the robustness and interpretive potential of the taxonomy proposed by Myrvold (2007)² and its subsequent expansion by Jasjit Singh (2014, 44), who identifies subgroups based on tradition, caste affiliation, and management through *sant* and *jathebandi*, this conceptual framework is here adopted to analyse diasporic *gurdwaras* in

European and Asian contexts. Myrvold's classification proves particularly useful because it captures not only the historical dimension of the temples but also their transformations linked to migratory processes, social dynamics, and spatial negotiations.

Historic and diasporic *gurdwaras* each exhibit specific forms, aesthetics, and materialities, many of which remain underexplored, especially in the case of diasporic *gurdwaras*. At the same time, as Bhonsle, Kaur, and Nikam (2023) observe, many modern *gurdwaras* reproduce, or aspire to reproduce, the Harmandir Sahib model, combining different architectural styles and materials to create a strong symbolic reference to tradition.

Building on this reference, diasporic *gurdwaras* can be distinguished into two analytical categories based on geographic, architectural, and material characteristics. 'Iconic diasporic *gurdwaras*' reproduce architectural and aesthetic elements of historic *gurdwaras*, serving as sites that convey continuity with Sikh tradition and signals of recognizability and visibility in the urban space (Saint-Blancat and Cancellieri 2014). 'Iconic aspiration' diasporic *gurdwaras*, following the category proposed by Beekers and Tamimi Arab (2016), exhibit an explicit orientation toward material and visual references to traditional Sikh architecture while adapting to functional, economic, and contextual conditions in Italian urban and peri-urban landscapes. Conversely, 'infrasecular diasporic *gurdwaras*' are located in industrial or peri-urban areas in adapted buildings, such as warehouses, former residences, or workshops, producing hybrid forms that reflect material constraints, local regulations, and available economic resources.

These dynamics are illustrated through two emblematic case studies: *gurdwaras* in Singapore, which display iconic characteristics in their aesthetic reference to tradition, and Italian *gurdwaras*, often infrasecular, which occupy adapted buildings and reflect material and regulatory adaptations related to the local context. Comparative analysis using these categories highlight processes of adaptation and creativity, showing how the materiality and spatiality of places of worship are negotiated in relation to the urban and social context in which they are situated.

Methodology and multi-sited research

This article adopts a mixed qualitative methodology, combining direct observation, semi-structured interviews with temple representatives and committee members, and analysis of visual material, both historical and field-generated. These methods are employed to document and analyse architectural forms, spatial organization, and processes of urban integration, while the empirical findings derived from this methodology are discussed in the subsequent sections dedicated to *gurdwaras* in Singapore and Italy. Methodologically, the research focuses on two analytical dimensions: (1) architecture and interior design, including reference models, key spatial and material elements, and their adaptations over time; and (2) the history of the temples, including site selection, previous locations, urban planning constraints, and financial resources employed.

Fieldwork in Italy began in 2011 and is based on long-term engagement with Italian Sikh communities, developed also through collaboration with the Sikhi Sewa Society³ and the Unione Sikh Italia.⁴ In Singapore, fieldwork was conducted more recently, between February 2025 and January 2026, as part of a three-year European project on

the spatiality, materiality, and public perception of *gurdwaras* in urban contexts, which enabled collaboration with the Central Sikh Gurdwara Board.⁵ The temporal asymmetry between the two field sites reflects different stages of community institutionalization and research access, and does not affect the comparative analytical framework adopted in the article.

Data collected in Singapore through direct observation and interviews were complemented by participants' perspectives on their own places of worship. For the two case studies of the European project, the Central Sikh Temple and the Silat Road Temple, Sikh volunteers of both genders completed photographic forms, taking five images each accompanied by brief descriptions, followed by in-depth interviews.⁶ All interviews were conducted in Italian (Italy) or English (Singapore), anonymized, recorded, and fully transcribed.

A visual architectural analysis was carried out across all 43 *gurdwaras* in Italy and 7 in Singapore. Direct observation was conducted during major festivals and Sunday services, including weekly *langar* events, at a subset of *gurdwaras*. Field notes and photographic documentation captured spatial configurations, material adaptations, and everyday practices where accessible, and were triangulated with archival material, historical photographs, and urban planning documents to ensure methodological rigor and comparative depth. These materials were systematically triangulated with archival sources, historical photographs, and urban planning documents in order to ensure methodological rigor and enhance the comparability of the two national contexts.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board.

The research was conducted by an external, non-Sikh researcher, occupying a position both inside and outside the field (Denning, Scriven, and Slatter 2022). This positionality shaped data collection in two main ways: it facilitated open discussions on architectural features, spatial arrangements, and planning constraints, while potentially limiting access to more sensitive intra-community dynamics. Reflexive field notes written after each visit were used to critically assess how researcher positionality influenced interactions, interpretations, and the construction of empirical material.

Empirical analysis

Building on the methodological and theoretical framework outlined above, the following sections present the empirical analysis of *gurdwaras* in Singapore and Italy. Drawing on multi-sited fieldwork, visual architectural analysis, and interview material, the discussion examines how architectural forms, material choices, and spatial configurations of *gurdwaras* are shaped through the interaction between religious principles, urban planning regimes, and local socio-economic conditions. The analytical categories introduced earlier are here mobilized as interpretive tools to analyse situated empirical cases.

Iconic gurdwaras and urban visibility in Singapore

The history of *gurdwaras* in the city-state of Singapore paradigmatically reflects the intertwining of migration, Sikh community organization, and urban planning policies within a highly regulated colonial and postcolonial context (Kaur 2008). Sikh temples have never been geographically static institutions. As a member of a *gurdwara* management

committee observed: ‘All the *gurdwaras*, I think maybe 50 percent of them were relocated at least once or twice before because the government does planning and zoning’.⁷ *Gurdwaras* developed as mobile religious spaces, often temporary, subject to relocations, reconstructions, mergers, and legal redefinitions, in response both to internal dynamics within the Sikh community and to urban transformations imposed by the State.

Since independence in 1965, Singapore has developed a highly centralized urban planning system aimed at supporting modernization, integration into the global economy, and the efficient management of a densely populated territory strategically positioned between the Indian and Pacific Oceans. The functionalist approach to urban space assigns precise development priorities to each area, also regulating the location and management of places of worship through state agencies such as the Urban Redevelopment Authority⁸ and the Housing and Development Board.

The State has followed the principle of parity among racial and religious groups. This principle has guided the planned distribution of religious sites in proportion to population composition (Kong 1992). Access to land for worship occurs through bidding procedures and long-term lease contracts, generally thirty years in duration, without any guarantee of automatic renewal (Musa 2023; Ye 2017). Religious organizations may compete only for sites assigned to their own tradition: this reduces inter-religious rivalry but increases intra religious competition (Woods 2019). In cases of urban redevelopment, moreover, the demolition of a site does not guarantee a replacement space for the same community, rendering their presence precarious and dependent on State priorities (Sinha 2016).

Within this regulatory framework, places of worship are conceived as collective infrastructures, similar to schools or libraries, yet subordinate to residential housing, education, and healthcare (Sinha 2003). Religious space is thus considered one urban function among others, to be integrated into the urban fabric, rather than exceptional in itself. Recent studies on Hindu temples show that religious buildings subject to architectural and emotional monitoring (Woods and Kong 2022) are not only conceived as spiritual spaces and collective infrastructures, but also as symbolic instruments employed to maintain and externally display social order and interethnic harmony (Kong 1993).

In this context, *gurdwaras* have been directly affected by urban policies, which have shaped their mobility, size, and architectural form, although their history predates independence from the United Kingdom (1963) and from Malaysia (1965).

The first formally recognized Sikh institution in Singapore was the *gurdwara* founded in 1912 on Queen Street, when a group of Sikhs purchased a bungalow with extensive grounds and converted it into a place of worship. This temple, later known as the Central Sikh Temple or ‘Wadda *Gurdwara*’, quickly became the principal point of reference. From the 1970s onward, the site was affected by State-led urban redevelopment plans, which led to the acquisition of the land and the obligation to relocate the temple. Negotiations between 1978 and 1979 illustrate the tension between state planning and community claims: despite internal mobilization and formal requests to maintain the original site, the temple was vacated in 1979 and temporarily relocated. Only in 1983 was a new site identified at Towner Road; construction began in 1984 and the new Central Sikh Temple was officially inaugurated in 1986.

In parallel, another institutional line emerged with Sikhs employed in the British police forces during the colonial period. The *Gurdwara Sahib Silat Road* is linked to

the first *gurdwara* established at the Pearl's Hill barracks, mainly frequented by Sikhs employed as *sepoys* and administrative officers. The relocation to Silat Road – today Jalan Bukit Merah – in 1922–1924, on land leased from the Singapore Harbour Board, responded to functional needs (proximity to the port and migratory networks) but also to increasing regulation of urban space. This *gurdwara* progressively became the second officially recognized public Sikh temple, especially after the transfer in 1966 of the *samadh* of Bhai Maharaj Singh – a tombstone of a Sikh freedom fighter –, which increased its symbolic and devotional value. The present complex, extensively renovated in 1995. In 1999, the temple was designated a historic site by the National Heritage Board.⁹

From the 1920s onward, however, the unity of the Sikh *sangat* was challenged by internal divisions along regional lines of origin in Punjab: Majha, Malwa, and Doaba¹⁰ (McCann 2011; Shee and Woods 2025). These resulted in the founding of separate *gurdwaras* based on different origins, transforming the Central Sikh Temple from a unitary space into a 'central' temple only in a symbolic and administrative sense. This fragmentation also had direct legal consequences: in 1940, with the *Queen Street Gurdwara Ordinance*, the colonial government established an incorporated Board of Trustees with equal representation of the three factions, formalizing a model of religious management strongly regulated by the State.

The Gurdwara Sri Guru Singh Sabha, founded in 1918 by Sikhs from the Majha region, was relocated several times – from Queen Street to Wilkie Road – until the construction of a new headquarters completed in 1980. Similarly, the Khalsa Dharmak Sabha, founded in 1923 by followers from the Malwa region, underwent numerous relocations before stabilizing at Niven Road, where the current building was completed in 1996. Representing Sikhs originating from the Doaba region is the Pardesi Khalsa Dharmak Diwan, founded in 1927. Due to limited financial resources, the *gurdwara* initially developed in rented and adaptive spaces, changing location several times – including Queen Street and Kirk Terrace – until the purchase, in 1991, of several units within a multi-storey building on Lorong 29, Geylang Road.¹¹

A particularly significant case is that of the Gurdwara Sahib in Katong, founded in 1953 by Sikhs predominantly belonging to a post-Partition (1947) entrepreneurial group. Initially emerging as a domestic and 'mobile' religious practice, the *gurdwara* stabilized only in the 1960s with the purchase of bungalows on Wilkinson Road and the construction, in 1969, of a dedicated building.

The founding of *gurdwaras* in Singapore was shaped not only by fragmentation but also by institutional mergers. This emerges with particular clarity in the case of the Gurdwara Sahib in Yishun, founded in 1995 from the convergence of two historically distinct *gurdwaras*: the Sikh temple of Sembawang and that of Jalan Kayu. Both originated as places of worship linked to the Sikh presence in British military bases and stood on state land subject to redevelopment. Government acquisitions and eviction notices in the 1980s necessitated a joint resettlement solution, culminating in the establishment of a single *gurdwara* on state land under a fixed-term lease contract.

Forms and materiality of gurdwaras in Singapore

Urban planning policies and the mobility of *gurdwaras*, discussed in the previous section, have had a profound impact on their architectural configurations within the urban space

of Singapore. In six out of seven cases, relocations involved significant changes in form and materials, with temporary or adapted spaces replaced by newly designed buildings fully integrated into the regulated urban fabric.

The architectural analysis of Singaporean *gurdwaras* is based on the identification and interpretation of recurring formal and symbolic elements, as described by Nikam (2024), applied to the six temples under study. The analysis aims to explore relationships between architecture, materiality, spatial organization, and urban integration, rather than to provide an isolated typological description, highlighting both continuity and adaptations with respect to traditional models.

The silhouette of the buildings is defined primarily by the presence of one or two main domes – *gumbad* – on the roof, varying in shape, size, and position. In all six temples analyzed, the dome is positioned on a flat roof, above the *palki sahib*, a canopy platform where the *Sri Guru Granth Sahib* is housed in the *darbar hall*, generally located on the upper floor of the building. The Silat Road Gurdwara features two domes aligned one behind the other. According to a research participant, ‘the temple’s large central dome and multiple smaller domes create a strong architectural identity rooted in traditional *gurdwara* design.’

These structures are clad in white, taking hemispherical, onion-shaped, or three-quarter-sphere forms, and often feature fluting. They are further adorned with floral bases – lotus petals – and gilded pinnacles (Figure 2). On the roofs of the *gurdwaras*, *chhatris* are also present, semi-open domed pavilions generally positioned at the four corners, which reinforce the temples’ recognizability in the urban skyline and emphasize their volumetric composition. This feature is found in five of the six temples examined, such as the Gurdwara Sahib in Katong (Figure 3), with the exception of the Silat Road Gurdwara.

Another element identified by Nikam (2024) is the rhythmic repetition of smaller domes along the external facades. This solution contributes to enhancing the

Figure 2. The six iconic *gurdwaras* of Singapore. Source: Author.

Figure 3. The *chhatris* at Gurdwara Sahib in Katong. Source: Author.

monumentality of the building and giving it a compact, almost fortified appearance, observable in the Central Sikh Temple, the Silat Road Sikh Gurdwara, and the Gurdwara Sahib in Katong. In contrast, the Shri Guru Singh Sabha Gurdwara and the Gurdwara Sahib in Yishun feature more restrained surfaces, lacking this rhythmic articulation and favoring a simpler volumetric composition (Figure 2).

Arcaded passages are another feature of traditional *gurdwara* architecture, mediating between the urban exterior and the sacred interior. In the city-state of Singapore, they frequently mark the temple entrance, taking the form of spired or multi-lobed arched canopies. At the Central Sikh Temple and at Gurdwara Sahib in Yishun – where the surrounding area lacks trees – these projecting canopies additionally provide protection from the climate.

Openings with cusp arches also play an important role in the composition of the facades. Windows framed by spired or multi-lobed arches punctuate the wall surfaces and contribute to the natural lighting of the interior spaces. This feature is present in the Central Sikh Temple, the Silat Road Sikh Gurdwara, the Khalsa Dharmak Sabha Gurdwara, the Gurdwara Sahib in Katong, and the Gurdwara Sahib in Yishun, albeit with formal variations. The Shri Guru Singh Sabha Gurdwara has less pronounced arched openings.

Ornamental elements similar to *bukarchas* – balconies decorated with spired arches and fluted pillars – are present only at the Central Sikh Temple (Figure 4). The Gurdwara Sahib in Katong features a projecting enclosed balcony that may evoke this type of element, but in a simplified form without decorative features or arched openings, suggesting a functional adaptation rather than a formal continuation of the tradition.

Based on the analysis of the main architectural elements – domes, *chhatris*, porticoes, and arched windows – the *gurdwaras* in Singapore can be classified as examples of ‘diasporic iconic *gurdwaras*’. Following the perspective of ‘iconicity’ (Knott, Krech,

Figure 4. The *bukarchas* at the Central Sikh Temple. Source: Author.

and Meyer 2016), these buildings not only host religious and communal practices but also communicate the Sikh presence in an immediately recognizable way, explicitly referencing the architectural model of historical traditional *gurdwaras*. ‘Iconicity’ thus manifests the tension between historical continuity and local adaptation, making these temples interpretable and recognizable as religious sites even in different urban contexts.

Certain elements not included in Nikam’s (2024) analysis warrant consideration in architectural studies, based on in situ observations, cross-comparison among the temples, and insights gathered from Sikh research participants. These elements are the façade colors, the *nishan sahib* – a flag located outside all seven temples – and the multi-storey structure of the buildings.

In Singapore, all six *gurdwaras* feature white facades, a choice related to paint rather than stone cladding such as marble, which is more difficult to maintain in the tropical climate (Figure 2). At the Silat Road Gurdwara, white is combined with gilded elements; at the Khalsa Dharmak Sabha Gurdwara, it appears entirely white; the Central Sikh Temple, the Shri Guru Singh Sabha Gurdwara, and the Gurdwara Sahib in Yishun combine white with blue elements, particularly in signage and Khanda or Ik Onkar symbols, and with gold details on domes and cornices.

From the perspective of internal organization, all *gurdwaras* show a recurring functional layout – with the exception of the Shri Guru Singh Sabha Gurdwara: the main *darbar hall* is located on the first or second floor, while the *langar hall* is generally on the ground floor.

A distinctive feature of the Central Sikh Temple is the presence of a pool – *sarovar* – on the second level, before access to the main *darbar hall*, surrounded by arches and pillars with floral detailing (Figure 5). Both elements – the pool and the portico – explicitly recall the structure of the Golden Temple in Amritsar, as noted by temple informants. In this regard, a Sikh research participant observes:

In Sikh Gurdwara Architecture, the water features an important element. Just as in Harmandir Sahib – Golden Temple, and many other important Sikh religious sites, water plays an important spiritual role in cleansing. This fountain at CST is so beautiful, refreshing, soothing when one chooses to sit along the perimeter of the fountain and recite their morning or evening prayers. This water feature has a calming element. However, a small downside to this feature is that periodic maintenance is required to maintain cleanliness and upkeep of the pool, the pumps and water features. A very small trade off.

In an urban context, the pool reproduces the *sarovar* tradition in a compact form, adapting symbolism and ritual function to the city scale. As another participant notes:

The fountain outside the Darbar Hall in the Central Sikh Temple, Singapore carries both practical and symbolic significance within Sikh tradition and modern *gurdwara* design. In an urban setting like Singapore, the fountain serves as a contemporary reminder of the Sarovar (holy pool) tradition, adapted into a compact, architectural form.

Figure 5. The *sarovar* on the second floor of the Central Sikh Temple. Source: Author.

Infrasecular gurdwaras and architectural adaptation in Italy

The geography of temples in Italy began to develop from the mid-1980s, when the first Sikhs – mostly men – arrived in the country, undertaking complex and perilous journeys through Central Asia, Eastern Europe, Turkey, and Greece. Upon arrival, many encountered situations of extreme vulnerability: lacking documentation, burdened by accumulated debts, and without support networks, they were engaged in precarious employment and vulnerable to exploitation (Denti, Ferrari, and Perocco 2005).

In this context, the organization of domestic prayer spaces – considered by Peach and Gale (2003) as a preliminary step toward the public spatialization of religion – was often impractical due to difficult living conditions. Anthropologist Ester Gallo attests that as early as the early 1990s, warehouse *gurdwaras* were being established. In Rome, in particular, an old building in a semi-industrial peripheral area was rented, allowing the faithful to gather weekly. There were no objections from local authorities, who preferred – as the anthropologist notes – to confine migrant life and ‘ethnic masculinity’ to marginal and less visible spaces (Ferraris 2009; Gallo 2012).

Between the mid-1980s and the late 1990s, the *gurdwara* in Italy was primarily perceived not as a space of sociability or community solidarity, but as a site for labor recruitment, where intra-ethnic power dynamics and exploitation were reproduced. According to interviews conducted by Gallo, some informants avoided attending the *gurdwara* for fear of becoming entangled in forms of economic and social dependence. Temples, while serving as refuges according to Charles Hirschman’s 3R model (2004), often consolidated the very same hierarchies of subordination: newcomers were required to interact with mediators who managed the temple and controlled access to resources, such as employment opportunities or housing.

In subsequent years, progressive emancipation from work-related constraints and debts to mediators, rather than family reunification processes, facilitated the relocation of communities outside metropolitan areas and brought about a substantial transformation in the function and role of the *gurdwara*: from an emergency space and site of survival strategies to a public place of communal identity and congregational worship. The formation of more stable communities in smaller urban contexts coincided with the emergence of a faith community attentive to the spatialization of religion and its public visibility.

A crucial moment in this process was the inauguration, in 2000, of the Gurdwara Singh Sabha in Novellara (Emilia Romagna region, Central Italy), in the presence of Romano Prodi, who was at the time President of the European Commission (Figure 6F; Gallo 2012). This event marked a key milestone, consecrating the Gurdwara Singh Sabha as the first Sikh temple recognized publicly and socially in Italy, without implying any legal or institutional recognition. Since 2011, the Gurdwara has also hosted the headquarters of the Sikhi Sewa Society and, since 2021, that of the Unione Sikh Italia, reinforcing its role as a community and organizational center of reference for the national Sikh community.

It took nearly a decade before a significant increase in the number of temples was observed. Surveys conducted from 2011 onward, aimed at mapping and monitoring new inaugurations, revealed a redistribution of the Sikh population toward smaller centers located in agricultural areas of Central and Northern Italy, in medium and

Figure 6. Exemplary *gurdwaras* representing architectural typologies in Italy. Source: Author.

large food industries, as well as other enterprises in Northern Italy (Omenetto 2015). Over the course of four years, there was a substantial increase in *gurdwaras*, with 51 new temples inaugurated: the peak occurred in 2011, with 13 inaugurations, followed by 10 in 2013 and 9 in 2014, primarily in medium and small provincial towns.

As of today, 58 *gurdwaras* are affiliated with the Unione Sikh Italia, in addition to approximately four or five further temples associated with a second organization, the Sikh Gurdwara Parbhandak Committee Italy, which has initiated dialogue with the Italian state.

Forms and materiality of *gurdwaras* in Italy

The location and architecture of Sikh temples in Italy result from the intersection of endogenous and exogenous factors. On one hand, the lack of legal recognition of Sikhism limits access to urban planning regulations pertaining to places of worship. On the other hand, architectural and spatial choices are guided by the need to accommodate religious practices, such as the Sunday diwan, and community activities, such as the *langar*, as well as by local community strategies determining the temple's location based on economic resources and accessibility for devotees.

The material and aesthetic configuration of *gurdwaras* is strongly conditioned – but not prevented – by the absence of legal formalization of Sikhism, which has not obtained an agreement (*Intesa*) under Article 8 of the Italian Constitution and is not included among the ‘recognized cults’ under Law No. 1159/1929. This absence restricts access to regional and municipal urban planning regulations for places of worship and prevents the construction of fully architecturally recognizable *gurdwaras* visible in the urban landscape (Fabretti, Giorda, and Vereni 2019; Giorda and Vanolo 2021; Omenetto and Giorda 2021). Consequently, Sikh communities – similarly to other non-recognized religious groups – are compelled to identify alternative solutions, often establishing cultural associations whose headquarters coincide with the place of worship and socialization (Bossi 2024).

Architecturally, these spaces primarily derive from the reuse of pre-existing structures, with varying levels of renovation and adaptation of facades to references typical of Sikh architecture (Figure 6). In most cases, these interventions do not radically transform the building envelope, and the *gurdwaras* retain the morphology of their previous use, often formally difficult to distinguish from surrounding buildings. This configuration can be interpreted through the lens of the ‘infrasecular’ category (della Dora 2018, 2025), in which religious and secular elements coexist and overlap within the same space. Although characterized by ordinary materials and structures, these buildings incorporate only select decorative elements of religious significance, producing *gurdwaras* in hybrid, liminal, and adaptive forms. While their meaning remains largely unknown to outsiders, the *nishan sahib* constitutes one of the few architectural indicators immediately identifying a building as a *gurdwara*. It functions as a spatial and religious device capable of making the Sikh presence visible even in architectural contexts that, in terms of form and materials, remain tied to the original uses and functions of the buildings. In this sense, the *nishan sahibs* operates as an infrasecular filter allowing Sikhism to manifest in the city and within urbanistically and materially adapted spaces.

Active *gurdwaras* in Italy can be distinguished into three primary architectural typologies, with corresponding geographic locations (Figure 6): (1) Residences in urban or peri-urban areas; (2) Industrial sheds and commercial buildings located in urban industrial areas or peri-urban zones; (3) Farmhouses and rural estates in peri-urban or agricultural areas.

The first typology, represented by a limited number of cases, consists of buildings previously used as residences. These differ from forms of ‘domestic sacralization’ recently analyzed by Bertolani and Boccagni (2023; Bertolani, Bonfanti, and Boccagni 2021; Boccagni and Bonfanti 2023), as they are not private homes with internal spaces temporarily or permanently adapted for the religious practice of a single family, but structures formally registered as association headquarters and intended for communal use. A representative case is the Gurdwara Sri Dashmesh Darbar Sahib in Cancellodora, in the province of Caserta (Campania region, Southern Italy; Figure 6C), located in a peri-urban area and housed in a two-story private villa formerly used as a residence.

The second typology comprises converted rural buildings, such as farmhouses or storage facilities, located in areas of agricultural vocation or outside urban centers. These structures are often chosen for the availability of large spaces, the peacefulness of the surrounding area, relative affordability compared to urban properties. Notable among these is the Gurudwara Sikh Sangat Darbar in Sorgà, province of Verona (Veneto region, Northeastern Italy; Figure 6D), housed in a *cascina* built in a style typical of nineteenth-century rural houses in Northeastern Italy.

The most widespread typology consists of *gurdwaras* located in industrial sheds or commercial buildings, found both within urban fabrics and in peri-urban industrial areas (Figure 6A, B, E and F). The Gurdwara Singh Sabha, for example, is housed in a building previously used as a supermarket in Pasiandora, in the Friuli Venezia Giulia region, Northeastern Italy (Figure 6A). Similarly, the Baba Jorawar Singh Ji – Baba Fateh Singh Ji Gurdwara occupies an industrial shed in Lonigo, province of Vicenza (Veneto region, Northeastern Italy; Figure 6E). The community has transformed the structure through visual and symbolic interventions, repainting it white and installing three golden domes on the roof, giving the temple a strong visual and symbolic identity

within the industrial context. The Gurdwara Guru Nanak Darbar, located in Castelfranco Emilia, province of Modena (Emilia Romagna region, Central Italy), incorporates figurative architectural elements through the use of a panel above the entrance depicting a large *gumbad* and six *chhatris* (Figure 6B), accompanied by a large sign displaying the temple's name.

This type of *gurdwara*, derived from industrial or commercial sheds, allows for formal and compositional remodeling of the facades due to their cubic geometry, regular and minimal surfaces, and the spatial modularity of the envelopes. This configuration enables the insertion of recognizable symbolic elements, such as arches, domes, or figurative panels, without particularly stringent structural constraints. In this sense, applying the category of 'iconic aspiration' proposed by Bertolani (2016) provides a framework to interpret the explicit orientation of these buildings toward material and visual references to traditional Sikh architecture, while adapting to functional, economic, and contextual conditions of the Italian urban and peri-urban landscape.

This architectural typology also presents a further variant that explicitly manifests 'iconic aspiration': in some cases, *gurdwara*-sheds are newly constructed through the acquisition of land in industrial areas by the community and the development of building projects specifically designed for religious purposes. Although conceived from the outset as spaces of worship, these buildings retain materials, volumes, and construction solutions typical of industrial architecture, situating themselves in formal continuity with the surrounding productive context. Some of these *gurdwaras* feature two-level articulations, arches in window openings, and, more rarely, domes. These symbolic elements, however, are embedded in architectural envelopes that do not replicate the traditional white cladding of historic temples, highlighting functional and contextual adaptation to local material and urban conditions.

A notable example is the Gurdwara Shri Kalgidhar Sahib in Pessina Cremonese, inaugurated in August 2011 and considered the second-largest Sikh temple in Europe (Figure 7B).

Figure 7. A: Abandoned construction site of the *gurdwara* in Sabaudia. B: Gurdwara Shri Kalgidhar Sahib, Pessina Cremonese. Source: Author.

The structure is organized on two floors and, while externally retaining characteristics of an industrial shed, features four towers on which, in 2023, four gold-colored enamel domes were added. This delayed intervention illustrates how processes of architectural symbolization can be progressive, responding to community, economic, and symbolic timelines that do not necessarily coincide with the initial construction phase.

Due to the legal precariousness affecting many Sikh places of worship in Italy, the construction of this type of temple may be accompanied by tensions with local authorities, who can impose administrative restrictions, halt construction, or issue closure orders. Such challenges directly impact the processes of material consolidation and institutionalization of *gurdwaras*. A notable case is the construction site for the *gurdwara* on Via Ayrton Senna in Sabaudia, province of Latina (Lazio region, Central Italy), initiated in 2012 to serve the Sikh community of the Agro Pontino and Castelli Romani areas (Figure 7A). The project, initially authorized, was suspended due to alleged irregularities, leaving the site unfinished and abandoned. The partial construction was enabled by an urban planning workaround: since the 1977 Master Plan did not foresee places of worship in that industrial area, the municipality first authorized a craft structure for Indian products, postponing the religious function to a subsequent amendment. During the works, however, disputes over non-compliant constructions arose, leading to the closure of the site in 2015.

Conclusion

The image of the Harmandir Sahib placed at the entrance of Gurdwara Sahib in Yishun, mentioned in the introduction, emerges, at the conclusion of the analysis, not as a mere iconographic reference but as an epistemological device. It activates a network of spatial and symbolic relationships connecting the foundational site of Sikh religious experience with its diasporic translations, rendering visible how *gurdwara* architecture continually constructs and negotiates its relationship with a shared symbolic center.

Comparisons between Singapore, as a city-state, and Italy, as a national context, demonstrate that *gurdwaras* are not simply peripheral replicas of Punjabi models but situated architectural configurations, generated through the interplay of religious principles, material conditions, and regulatory frameworks. In Singapore, purpose-built or extensively renovated buildings integrated into a highly regulated urban planning system produce *gurdwaras* that are recognizable within the city skyline and endowed with explicit visual markers. By contrast, in Italy, many *gurdwaras* lack domes, arched windows, white cladding, or golden pinnacles: elements typically associated with historical Sikh temple architecture. The absence of these features does not indicate a lack of symbolic intentionality but rather reflects regulatory, economic, and spatial constraints, alongside pragmatic strategies for settlement within urban and peri-urban contexts. The frequent reuse of industrial sheds, farmhouses, and residential buildings generates hybrid, visually subtle forms, where sacredness is expressed through incremental and sometimes minimal interventions. This results, particularly in the Italian context, in a condition of ‘tolerated invisibility’: spaces that are formally marginal yet central to the social and spiritual life of the community, reflecting *de facto* rather than *de jure* religious pluralism, based on everyday negotiation rather than fully inclusive governance (Giorgi, Giorda, and Palmisano 2022; Pace 2013).

Beyond their material and formal dimensions, *gurdwaras* perform social and symbolic functions that underscore their diasporic character in both contexts, albeit in different ways. In Singapore, Shee and Woods (2025, 2026) describe them not only as places of worship but also as ‘sensory contact zones’, intra-ethnic meeting spaces and arenas of identity negotiation that contribute to the formation of an urban Sikh identity that is simultaneously diasporic, local, and decolonial. *Gurdwaras* thus operate as hubs of socialization, cultural transmission, and mutual support, while not being immune to internal tensions between ‘local’ Sikhs and more recent Punjabi migrants – labeled *desi* – perceived as culturally distant despite sharing the same faith (Woods and Kong 2023). In Italy, *gurdwaras* serve as orientation points for newcomers, socialization spaces for second-generation Sikhs, and protective environments for more vulnerable workers. Some participate in public initiatives – such as Vaisakhi celebrations or charitable *langar* events – while often maintaining visibility associated more with welfare than formal religious recognition. In this sense, the Sikh presence is situated within a de facto pluralism but not yet de jure, where sacred space is negotiated rather than legally protected (Cianitto 2024).

In light of these findings, the analysis presented here constitutes an exploratory comparative study based on a limited number of cases (small-N), not aimed at statistical generalization but at identifying conceptual patterns and material processes in different urban and regulatory contexts. Its contribution lies in the depth of architectural and ethnographic observation and in the capacity to relate situated empirical data to broader theoretical debates within Religious Studies and the Geography of Religion.

The proposed classification not only describes the role of *gurdwaras* within Sikh communities but also functions as an interpretive tool capable of systematically analyzing correspondences between social function, symbolic meaning, and architectural configuration. From this perspective, extending the analysis of architectural variations to other geographical contexts appears particularly relevant, in order to test its comparative validity and applicability in other diasporic settings. The notions of ‘iconic’, ‘iconic aspiration’ and ‘infrasecular’ diasporic *gurdwaras* are not intended as fixed typologies, but rather as flexible analytical tools subject to ongoing empirical validation.

A further axis for future research concerns the intersection of architecture, social interaction, and urban inclusion. The ongoing three-year research project seeks to investigate systematically how the form, materiality, and location of *gurdwaras* affect the urban fabric and surrounding social dynamics, exploring the role of religious architecture not only as symbolic expression but also as a device capable of structuring practices of encounter, visibility, and recognition. In this respect, Nikam’s observation is particularly pertinent:

Future research could explore how modern innovations and materials can harmonize with traditional Sikh design principles, allowing *gurdwaras* to serve their spiritual purpose in the modern world. This exploration is important for sustaining religious practices and for deepening our understanding of how architecture can facilitate a more inclusive [...]. (Nikam 2024, 23)

Following this perspective, the study of *gurdwara* architecture can be framed not only as an analysis of forms and symbols, but as a privileged lens for understanding how religious space actively contributes to the construction of social relations, diasporic belonging, and processes of inclusion in contemporary urban space.

Notes

1. The term *diaspora*, here used with awareness of its contested genealogy (Safran 1991; Cohen 1997; Brubaker 2005), refers not to a static community but to the ongoing processes of spatialization, adaptation, and identification that link dispersed Sikh populations through religious and architectural practices (Ballantyne 2006).
2. While Myrvold's (2007) taxonomy provides a robust analytical foundation for distinguishing between historic *gurdwaras* in Punjab and those in the diaspora, it is important to note that the contemporary Indian architectural landscape presents a complexity that transcends this dichotomy. Beyond the sites directly associated with the lives of the Gurus, northern India is home to numerous urban and rural *gurdwaras* of recent construction that, while not 'historic,' do not fit the typical dynamics of the overseas diaspora. A notable example of this architectural 'third way' is the eight-story *gurdwara* in Calcutta described by Sarah Lloyd (1984, 2–3), whose verticality and urban prominence represent a formal evolution distinct from the traditional commemorative canon. In this article, however, the 'historic' vs. 'diasporic' distinction is maintained as a functional category to highlight the divergences between the idealized Punjabi model and the processes of material adaptation in the contexts of Singapore and Italy.
3. The Sikhi Sewa Society is an association composed primarily of second-generation Sikhs, committed to promoting greater knowledge and understanding of Sikhism within Italian society.
4. The Unione Sikh Italia is a federative body that brings together the majority of Sikh centers currently active in Italy. Founded in 2021, its aim is to provide formal and legal representation for the Sikh community at the national level, while simultaneously fostering dialogue with state institutions, local administrations, cultural associations, and other religious communities.
5. The Central Sikh Gurdwara Board manages and administers the daily operations of Singapore's temples, in particular the Central Sikh Temple, and the Gurdwara Shaib Silat Road along Jalan Bukit Merah. For more information: <https://sikhs.org.sg/>
6. It should be noted that the opinions collected through photographic elicitation refer exclusively to the two Singaporean case studies (Central Sikh Temple and Silat Road Temple) and therefore do not represent the entire population of *gurdwaras* in the city. This limitation must be taken into account when interpreting the results concerning participants' perceptions. Nevertheless, this method, already employed in Singapore, will soon be extended to the two selected case studies in Italy.
7. Interview with the President of the Pardesi Khalsa Dharmak Diwan Gurdwara, Singapore, 25 January 2026.
8. The Urban Redevelopment Authority is Singapore's statutory agency responsible for land use planning, urban design, and conservation. Established under the Urban Redevelopment Authority Act (1974), it oversees urban zoning, the allocation of land for residential, commercial, industrial, or 'Place of Worship' purposes, and can coordinate the acquisition and relocation of land for major development or urban renewal projects.
9. Sikh Temple Now a Historic Site,' *The Straits Times*, 15 November 1999, 42.
10. According to McCann (2011), the Punjab was divided into two zones by the Sutlej River so that by the beginning of the twentieth century the major Sikh Districts were: *Majha* – Gujranwala, Sialkot, Gurdaspur, Lahore, Amritsar, Kapurthala, Hoshiapur and Jullundur; and *Malwa* – Ferozepore, Ludhiana, Patiala, Nabha, Maler Kotla, Jindh, Ambala, and Kalsia. A third sector – the *Doaba* – was also identified. *Majha* and *Malwa* Jats – the primary soldier agriculturalists of the region – acquired positive stereotypes, which facilitated their employment in India and abroad.
11. Its persistent location in non-purpose-built buildings distinguishes it from other *gurdwaras* in Singapore and justifies its exclusion from the main architectural analysis of this article; however, precisely because of its hybrid and adaptive spatial modalities, the Pardesi Khalsa Dharmak Diwan merits future explorations specifically dedicated to its architecture.

Acknowledgements

I am especially grateful to Maria Chiara Giorda and Kirti Nishant Nikam for their valuable and insightful feedback, which greatly helped shape the conceptual framework and comparative analysis presented in this study, as well as for their encouragement regarding its relevance and contribution to ongoing scholarly discussions.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101149085. Views and opinions expressed are however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

**Funded by
the European Union**

References

- Arshi, P. S. 1986. *Sikh Architecture in Punjab*. 1st ed. New Delhi, India: Intellectual Publishing House.
- Axel, B. K. 2001. *The Nation's Tortured Body: Violence, Representation, and the Formation of a Sikh Diaspora*. Durham, USA: Duke University Press.
- Bainiwal Singh, T. 2023. "The Gurdwara." In *The Sikh World*, edited by P. Singh and A. P. Singh Mandair, 171–191. London, UK: Routledge.
- Ballantyne, T. 2006. *Between Colonialism and Diaspora: Sikh Cultural Formations in an Imperial World*. Durham, USA: Duke University Press.
- Barrier, N. G., and V. A. Dusenbery, eds. 1989. *The Sikh Diaspora: Migration and the Experience beyond Punjab*. New Delhi, India: Chanakya Publications.
- Bartmański, D., and J. C. Alexander. 2012. "Introduction: Materiality and Meaning in Social Life: Toward an Iconic Turn in Cultural Sociology." In *Iconic Power. Cultural Sociology*, edited by J. C. Alexander, D. Bartmański, and B. Giesen, 1–12. New York: Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137012869_1
- Beaumont, J. 2010. "Transcending the Particular in Postsecular Cities." In *Exploring the Postsecular City: The Religious, the Political and the Urban*, edited by A. Moledijk, J. Beaumont, and C. Jedan, 1–17. Leiden, Netherlands: Brill.
- Beekers, D., and P. Tamimi Arab. 2016. "Dreams of an Iconic Mosque: Spatial and Temporal Entanglements of a Converted Church in Amsterdam." *Material Religion* 12 (2): 137–164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17432200.2016.1172760>.
- Bertolani, B. 2015. "Punjabis in Italy: The Role of Ethnic and Family Networks in Immigration and Social Integration." In *Migrations, Mobility and Multiple Affiliations: Punjabis in a Transnational World*, edited by S. I. Rajan, V. J. Varghese, and A. K. Nanda, 319–337. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Bertolani, B. 2018. "Ways of Making Sikhii in Italy: Considerations from a Case Study of Sikh Youth." *Sikh Formations* 14 (3–4): 364–383. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2018.1527593>.
- Bertolani, B. 2020. Gurdwaras and the Domestication of Urban Space: Preliminary Notes From a Case Study in Southall, West London. *HOMInG Working Paper*, 8.

- Bertolani, B., and P. Boccagni. 2023. "Domestic Religion and the Migrant Home: The Private, the Diasporic and the Public in the Sacralization of Sikh Dwellings in Italy." *Ethnicities* 23 (2): 284–305.
- Bertolani, B., S. Bonfanti, and P. Boccagni. 2021. "At Home in the Gurdwara? Religious Space and the Resonance with Domesticity in a London Suburb." *Religion* 51 (3): 423–442. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0048721X.2021.1916787>.
- Bharadwaj, P., A. Khwaja, and A. Mian. 2008. "The big March: Migratory Flows after Partition of British India." *Economic and Political Weekly* 43 (35): 39–49.
- Bhatti, B. S. 1987. "Ram Singh: The Inventor of Sikh Architecture." In *The Sikh Art and Architecture*, edited by Darshan Singh, 1–3. Chandigarh: Punjab University.
- Bhonsle, K., H. Kaur, and N. Nikam. 2023. "Values and Philosophy in the Design Interpretation of the Sacred Gurdwaras." *Social Evolution and History* 12 (14): 299–321.
- Bhui, D. S. 1999. "The Golden Temple: A Synthesis of Styles." In edited by P. Baksheesh Singh, 231–233. Patiala, India: Publication Bureau, Punjabi University.
- Boccagni, P., and S. Bonfanti. 2023. *Migration and Domestic Space: Ethnographies of Home in the Making*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Bossi, L. 2024. *Le religioni e la città. La governance locale della diversità*. Bologna, Italy: Il Mulino.
- Brar, P., J. Dhanjal, and J. S. Scott. 2021. "Vernacular, Modernist, Historic." *Journal of the Society for the Study of Architecture in Canada* 46 (2): 11–37. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1088487ar>.
- Brubaker, R. 2005. "The 'Diaspora' Diaspora." *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 28 (1): 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0141987042000289997>.
- Burchardt, M., J. Martínez-Ariño, M. Griera, and P. Bramadat. 2023. "Rite and Stone: Religious Belonging and Urban Space in Global Perspective." *Space and Culture* 26 (2): 148–154. <https://doi.org/10.1177/12063312231161185>.
- Burchardt, M., and M. Westendorp. 2018. "The im-materiality of Urban Religion: Towards an Ethnography of Urban Religious Aspirations." *Culture and Religion* 19 (2): 160–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14755610.2018.1444656>
- Cianitto, C. 2024. *Minoranze e simboli religiosi. I Sikh tra identità e cittadinanza*. Giappichelli.
- Cloke, P., and R. Johnston, eds. 2005. *Spaces of Geographical Thought: Deconstructing Human Geography's Binaries*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE.
- Cohen, R. 1997. *Global Diasporas: An Introduction*. London, UK: UCL Press.
- Cole, O. 1973. "The Gurdwara: The Sikh Temple." *Learning for Living* 13 (2): 55–56. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00239707308557015>.
- Cozma, I., A. Federici, M. C. Giorda, and S. Omenetto. 2023. "From Secular Spaces to Religious Places: The Case of the Romanian Orthodox Place of Worship of Lunghezza (Rome, Italy)." *Religions* 14 (1): 100. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14010100>.
- della Dora, V. 2018. "Infrasecular Geographies." *Progress in Human Geography* 42 (1): 44–71. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132516666190>.
- della Dora, V. 2025. "Invisible Visibilities, Visible Invisibilities: Reflections on the Infrasecular." In *Handbook of the Geographies of Religion*, edited by L. Kong, O. Woods, and J. K. H. Tse, 43–52. Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Dempsey, K. E. 2023. "'Infrasecular' Geographies and the Multifaceted Significance of a European Shrine Cathedral." *Journal of Cultural Geography* 40 (1): 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08873631.2023.2194841>.
- Denning, S., Scriven R., Slatter R. 2022. "Three Participatory Geographers: Reflections on Positionality and Working with Participants in Researching Religions, Spiritualities, and Faith." *Social & Cultural Geography* 23 (6): 892–910. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2020.1815826>
- Denti, D., F. Ferrari, and F. Perocco, eds. 2005. *I Sikh. Storia e immigrazione*. FrancoAngeli.
- Department of Statistics Singapore. 2021. *Census of Population 2020 Statistical Release 1: Demographic Characteristics, Education, Language and Religion*. Department of Statistics. https://www.singstat.gov.sg/publications/reference/cop2020-sr1/census20_stat_release1.
- de Wildt, K., M. Radermacher, V. Krech, B. Löffler, and W. Sonne. 2019. "Transformations of 'Sacredness in Stone': Religious Architecture in Urban Space in 21st Century Germany—New

- Perspectives in the Study of Religious Architecture.” *Religions* 10 (11): 602. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel10110602>.
- Dhesi, M. 2009. *An Ethnographic Study of the Concept and Development of the Gurdwara in the UK* (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Birmingham.
- Dokras, U. 2021. *The Art & Architecture of the Golden Temple Complex, Amritsar: Collection of Essays*. Indo Nordic Author’s Collective.
- Fabretti, V., M. Giorda, and P. Vereni. 2019. “Increasing Plurality and Neglected Pluralism: Religious Diversity in the Suburbs of Rome.” In *Emergent Religious Pluralism*, edited by J. J. Bock, J. Fahy, and S. Everett, 167–193. London, UK: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Ferraris, F. 2009. “Going Rural and Urban at Once: Reflections from the Roman Sikh Context.” *Journal of Contemporary Religion* 24 (3): 305–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13537900903080428>.
- Finlayson, C. 2017. “Church-in-a-Box: Making Space Sacred in a non-traditional Setting.” *Journal of Cultural Geography* 34 (3): 303–323. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08873631.2016.1264262>.
- Freiberger, O. 2019. *Considering Comparison: A Method for Religious Studies*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Gallo, E. 2012. “Creating Gurdwaras, Narrating Histories: Perspectives on the Sikh Diaspora in Italy.” *South Asia Multidisciplinary Academic Journal*. <http://journals.openedition.org/samaj/3431>.
- Garha, N. S., and A. D. I. Valls. 2017. “Sikh Diaspora and Spain: Migration, Hypermobility and Space.” *Diaspora Studies* 10 (2): 193–216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09739572.2017.1324385>.
- Ghada, E. 2021. “The Influences of Islamic Architecture on Sikh Architecture in Punjab Region from the 16th–19th ce.” *SHEDET* 8: 111–138.
- Giorda, M. C. 2024. History and Heritage of the Great Mosque of Rome. In *Historia Religionum*, 16.
- Giorda, M. C., and A. Vanolo. 2021. “Religious Diversity and Inter-faith Competition: The Politics of Camouflage in Italian Cities.” *Territory, Politics, Governance* 9 (2): 222–240. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622671.2019.1702894>.
- Giorgi, A., M. C. Giorda, and S. Palmisano. 2022. “The Puzzle of Italian Religious Freedoms: Local Experiments and Complex Interactions.” *Religions* 13 (7): 626. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel13070626>
- Glover, W. J. 2012. “Shiny new Buildings: Rebuilding Historic Sikh Gurdwaras in Indian Punjab.” *Future Anterior: Journal of Historic Preservation, History, Theory, and Criticism* 9 (1): 33–47. <https://doi.org/10.5749/futuante.9.1.0033>
- Gökarıksel, B. 2009. “Beyond the Officially Sacred: Religion, Secularism, and the Body in the Production of Subjectivity.” *Social & Cultural Geography* 10 (6): 657–674. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649360903068993>
- Hackworth, J., and E. Gullikson. 2013. “Giving new Meaning to Religious Conversion: Churches, Redevelopment, and Secularization in Toronto.” *Canadian Geographies / Géographies Canadiennes* 57 (1): 72–89. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1541-0064.2012.00451.x>.
- Hawley, M., ed. 2013. *Sikh Diaspora: Theory, Agency, and Experience*. Leiden, Netherlands: Brill.
- Hazard, S. 2019. “Two Ways of Thinking about new Materialism.” *Material Religion* 15 (5): 629–631. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17432200.2019.1666585>.
- Hirschman, C. 2004. “The Role of Religion in the Origins and Adaptation of Immigrant Groups in the United States.” *International Migration Review* 38 (3): 1206–1233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1747-7379.2004.tb00233.x>
- Hirvi, L. 2014. “Civic Engagement and Seva: An Ethnographic Case Study of a Sikh Gurdwara in Yuba City, California.” *Journal of Punjab Studies* 21 (1): 55–68.
- Houtman, D., and B. Meyer, eds. 2012. *Things: Religion and the Question of Materiality*. New York, USA: Fordham University Press.
- Jacobsen, K. A. 2012. “Tuning Identity in European ‘Houses of the Guru’: The Importance of Gurdwaras and Kirtan among Sikhs in Europe.” In *Sikhs across Borders: Transnational Practices of European Sikhs*, edited by K. A. Jacobsen and C. Myrvold, 105–118. London, UK: Bloomsbury.

- Jacobsen, K. A., and K. Myrvold. 2012. *Sikhs Across Borders: Transnational Practices of European Sikhs*. London: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Jordan, K. 2022. "Urban Churches in an Infrasecular Landscape: Three Case Studies from the Anglican Diocese of London." *The Journal of Architecture*, 27 (2-3): 346–371. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13602365.2022.2072933>.
- Kahlon Singh, S. 2021. *Sikhs in Continental Europe: From Norway to Greece and Russia to Portugal*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Karamjit Singh Chahal, S. D. 2012. "Architectural Evolution of Gurdwaras: An Overview." *The IUP Journal of Architecture* 5 (1): 7–32.
- Katsaura, O. 2023. "Architecturations of Pentecostal Power: Contribution to a Sociology of Pentecostal Auditoriums." *Space and Culture* 26 (2): 268–278. <https://doi.org/10.1177/12063312221130241>
- Kaur, A. 2008. "The Evolution of the Sikh Identity in Singapore." In *Religious Diversity in Singapore*, edited by A. E. Lai, 275–297. Singapore: Institute of Southeast Asian Studies. <https://doi.org/10.1355/9789812307552-021>
- Kaur, J. 2020. "Convergence in Religious Philosophy, Beliefs and Practices of Sikhism for Environmental Actions." *SPACE* 24 (3–4): 21–29.
- Kaur, J. 2023. "Sikh Architecture." In *The Sikh World*, edited by P. Singh and A. P. Singh Mandair, 216–240. London, UK: Routledge.
- Kaur, J. 2025. "Sacred Sikh Architecture as Places of Spiritual Connect: A Case of Golden Temple, Amritsar." In *Culture of the Sacred Space (USAS 2023. Advances in Science, Technology & Innovation)*, edited by O. Niglio, 101–119. Cham: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-69634-3_8
- Kaur, M. 1983. *The Golden Temple, Past and Present*. Amritsar, India: GNDU.
- Kaur, N. 2016. "Creating a Pindh: Place-Making within a Sikh Diasporic Community in Malaya." *Sikh Formations* 12 (1): 28–52. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2016.1147177>.
- Kaur, T. 2021. "Sikh Architecture." In *Encyclopedia of Indian Religions*, edited by A. P. S. Mandair, 27–44. Springer. <https://link.springer.com/referencework/10.1007978-94-024-0846-1>.
- Knott, K. 2005. *The Location of Religion: A Spatial Analysis*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Knott, K. 2010. "Religion, Space, and Place: The Spatial Turn in Research on Religion." *Religion and Society* 1:29–34. <https://doi.org/10.3167/arrs.2010.010103>.
- Knott, K., V. Krech, and B. Meyer. 2016. "Iconic Religion in Urban Space." *Material Religion* 12 (2): 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17432200.2016.1172759>.
- Knowles, C. 2013. "Nigerian London: Re-mapping Space and Ethnicity in Superdiverse Cities." *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 36 (4): 651–669. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2012.678874>
- Koch, N., A. Valiyev, and K. Hazmi Zaini. 2018. "Mosques as Monuments: An Inter-Asian Perspective on Monumentality and Religious Landscapes." *Cultural Geographies* 25 (1): 183–199. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1474474017724480>
- Kochhar, A. 2020. Sri Harmandir Sahib: A History of Struggle and Devotion. <https://www.peepulree.world/livehistoryindia/story/monuments/harmandir-sahib>.
- Kong, L. 1992. "The Sacred and the Secular: Exploring Contemporary Meanings and Values for Religious Buildings in Singapore." *Asian Journal of Social Science* 20 (1): 18–42. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/soss_research/1817.
- Kong, L. 1993. "Ideological Hegemony and the Political Symbolism of Religious Buildings in Singapore." *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space* 11 (1): 23–45. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/soss_research/1728.
- Kong, L. 2001. "Mapping 'New' Geographies of Religion: Politics and Poetics in Modernity." *Progress in Human Geography* 25 (2): 211–233. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/soss_research/1717
- Kong, L., O. Woods, and J. K. H. Tse, eds. 2025. *Handbook of the Geographies of Religion*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer.
- Lefebvre, H. 1991. *The Production of Space*. Oxford, UK and Cambridge, USA: Blackwell.
- Le Galès, P., and J. Robinson, eds. 2024. *The Routledge Handbook of Comparative Global Urban Studies*. London, UK: Routledge.

- Lloyd, S. 1984. *An Indian Attachment*. London: Eland.
- Lynch, N. 2016. "Domesticating the Church: The Reuse of Urban Churches as Loft Living in the Post-secular City." *Social & Cultural Geography* 17 (7): 849–870. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2016.1139167>.
- Lynch, N., and R. LeDrew. 2022. "Adaptations on the Edge: Post-secular Placemaking and the Adaptive Reuse of Worship Spaces in Newfoundland." *Social & Cultural Geography* 23 (2): 309–329. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2020.1737961>.
- Malhotra, K. K. 2023. "The Sikh Sacred Space: From Guru Nanak to Maharaja Ranjit Singh." *Journal of Sikh & Punjab Studies* 30 (1): 43–69.
- Massey, D. 1993. "Power-geometry and a Progressive Sense of Place." In *Mapping the Future: Local Cultures, Global Change*, edited by J. Bird, B. Curtis, T. Putnam, G. Robertson, and L. Tickner, 59–69. London, UK: Routledge.
- McCann, G. 2011. "Sikhs and the City: Sikh History and Diasporic Practice in Singapore." *Modern Asian Studies* 45 (6): 1465–1498. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0026749X11000138>.
- Meyer, B., and A. Moors, eds. 2003. *Mediating Religion: Conversations in Media, Religion and Culture*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Morgan, D. 2021. *The Thing about Religion*. Chapel Hill, USA: University of North Carolina Press.
- Murphy, A. 2012. *The Materiality of the Past: History and Representation in Sikh Tradition*. Oxford, UK and New York, USA: Oxford University Press.
- Musa, M. A. 2023. "Singapore's Secularism and Its Pragmatic Approach to Religion." *Religions* 14 (2): 219. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel14020219>.
- Myrvold, K. 2007. *Inside the Guru's Gate: Ritual Uses of Texts among the Sikhs in Varanasi* [Doctoral dissertation, Lund University]. Centre for Theology and Religious Studies.
- Myrvold, K., and K. A. Jacobsen, eds. 2011. *Sikhs in Europe: Migration, Identities and Representations*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Nayar, K. E. 2010. "The Making of Sikh Space: The Role of the Gurdwara." In *Asian Religions in British Columbia*, edited by L. DeVries, D. Baker, and D. Overmyer, 43–63. Vancouver, Canada: UBC Press.
- Nikam, K. N. 2024. "Building Belief: The Evolution of Sikh Architecture and Its Impact on Religious Consciousness." *Sikh Formations* 12: 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2024.2437856>.
- Obadia, L. 2015. "Spatial Turn, beyond Geography: A new Agenda for Sciences of Religion?" *International Review of Sociology* 25 (2): 200–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03906701.2015.1039269>.
- Omenetto, S. 2015. "Dio non ha passaporto. I gurdwara dal Punjab all'Italia." *Studi e Materiali di Storia Delle Religioni* 2:616–650.
- Omenetto, S., and M. C. Giorda. 2021. "Seppur informali: L'invisibilità urbana dei gruppi religiosi. Un'ipotesi esplorativa per un centro culturale Sikh a Roma." *Archivio di Studi Urbani e Regionali* 132:177–199. <https://doi.org/10.3280/ASUR2021-132008>.
- Pace, E. 2013. "Achilles and the Tortoise. A Society Monopolized by Catholicism Faced with an Unexpected Religious Pluralism." *Social Compass* 60 (4): 315–331. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0037768613492280>.
- Peach, C., and R. Gale. 2003. "Muslims, Hindus and Sikhs in the new Religious Landscape of England." *Geographical Review* 93 (4): 469–490. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1931-0846.2003.tb00043.x>
- Perec, G. 1974. *L'infra-ordinaire [The infra-ordinary]*. Éditions Galilée.
- Platt, L., R. Abushena, and R. Snape. 2021. "Leisure, Religion and the (Infra)Secular City: The Manchester and Salford Whit Walks." *Leisure Studies* 40 (6): 826–836. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02614367.2021.1933573>.
- Richardson, M. 2022. "Geographic Roots, Anthropological Routes: New Avenues in Geographies of Religions." *Geography Compass* 16 (3): e12613. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12613>.
- Robinson, J. 2022. *Comparative Urbanism: Tactics for Global Urban Studies*. Oxford, UK: John Wiley & Sons.

- Safran, W. 1991. "Diasporas in Modern Societies: Myths of Homeland and Return." *Diaspora: A Journal of Transnational Studies* 1 (1): 83–99. <https://doi.org/10.1353/dsp.1991.0004>
- Saint-Blancat, C., and A. Cancellieri. 2014. "From Invisibility to Visibility? The Appropriation of Public Space through a Religious Ritual: The Filipino Procession Of Santacruzani in Padua, Italy." *Social & Cultural Geography* 15 (6): 645–663. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2013.879494>.
- Shee, S. Y., and O. Woods. 2025. "(Un)Mapping the Punjab onto Singapore's Gurdwaras: Diasporic Territorialities and Decolonial Spaces of Sikh Socialisation." *Geopolitics* 30 (3): 1499–1524. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14650045.2025.2451300>.
- Shee, S. Y., and O. Woods. 2026. "Conditional Inclusion in the Sensory Contact Zone: Coexisting With *desis* in Singapore's Gurdwaras." *Social & Cultural Geography* 27 (4): 439–459. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2025.2564639>.
- Sian, K. P. 2012. "Gurdwaras, Guns and Grudges in 'Post-racial' America." *Sikh Formations* 8 (3): 293–297. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2012.752676>.
- Singh, Aulakh R., and K. Singh Chahal. 2014. "The Spatio-Geometrical Analysis of First Sikh Shrine—Sri Harmandar Sahib, Amritsar." *Historicity and Hermeneutics. Journal of Sikh Studies* XXXVIII: 134–147.
- Singh, G. 1998. "Sikh Architecture." In *Encyclopedia of Sikhism*, edited by Harbans Singh, 131–133. Patiala, India: Punjabi University.
- Singh, G. 2006. "Gurdwaras and Community-Building among British Sikhs." *Contemporary South Asia* 15 (2): 147–164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09584930600955267>.
- Singh, G., and D. S. Tatla. 2006. *Sikhs in Britain: The Making of a Community*. London: ZED Books Limited.
- Singh, J. 2014. "House of the Guru? Young British Sikhs' Engagement with Gurdwaras." *Journal of Punjab Studies* 21:41–54.
- Singh, J. 2023. "Not Asian Enough? The Racialisation of Sikhs in Southeast Asia." In *Global Sikhs: Histories, Practices and Identities*, edited by O. K. Takhar and D. R. Jakobsh, 260–277. London, UK: Routledge.
- Singh, P., and T. S. Baniwal. 2024. "Sikhs in North America: Remembering key Historical Events, Challenges and Responses." *Sikh Formations* 20 (1–2): 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2024.2354034>.
- Singh, P., and E. L. Fenech, eds. 2014. *The Oxford Handbook of Sikh Studies*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Singh, R. D., J. Kaur, and P. Kaur. 2017. "Investigating the Architectural Manifestations of Path and Place in Sacred Sikh Architecture." In *Understanding Built Environment*, edited by F. Seta, A. Biswas, A. Khare, and J. Sen, 37–46. London, UK: Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-10-2138-1_4
- Singha, H. S. 2000. *The Encyclopedia of Sikhism*. New Delhi, India: Hemkunt Publishers.
- Sinha, V. 2003. "Merging 'different' Sacred Spaces: Enabling Religious Encounters through Pragmatic Utilisation of Space?" *Contributions to Indian Sociology* 37 (3): 459–494. <https://doi.org/10.1177/006996670303700303>
- Sinha, V. 2016. "Marking Spaces as 'Sacred': Infusing Singapore's Urban Landscape with Sacrality." *International Sociology* 31 (4): 467–488. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268580916643259>.
- Soja, E. 1996. *Thirdspace: Journeys to Los Angeles and Other Real-and-Imagined Places*. Oklahoma, USA: Blackwell.
- Stephenson, B., and N. Lynch. 2025. "Spaces of Alterity: Contemporary Geographies of Alternative Sacred Space." In *Handbook of the Geographies of Religion*, edited by L. Kong, O. Woods, and J. K. Tse, 369–389. London, UK: Springer.
- Stoker, V. 2013. "Other Accommodations: Sikh Advocacy, Religious Architecture, and Cultural Preservation in Quebec." In *Sikh Diaspora: Theory, Agency, and Experience*, edited by M. Hawley, 193–216. Leiden, Netherlands: Brill.
- Takhar, O., and D. R. Jakobsh. 2023. *Global Sikhs*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Talbot, I., and S. Thandi, eds. 2004. *People on the Move: Punjabi Colonial and Post-colonial Migration*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.

- Tamimi Arab, P., J. S. Hughes, and S. Brent Rodríguez-Plate. 2024. "Editors' Introduction: The Pasts, Presents, and Futures of the Study of Material Religion." In *The Routledge Handbook of Material Religion*, edited by P. T. Tamimi Arab, J. S. Hughes, and S. B. Rodríguez-Plate, 1–12. London, UK: Routledge.
- Tatla, D. S. 1999. *The Sikh Diaspora: Search for Statehood*. London, UK: UCL Press.
- Townsend, C. M. 2018. "Sikh Millennials of the 'Kirtan Generation' in the Making of an 'American Sikhism.'" *Sikh Formations* 14 (3–4): 424–434. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448727.2018.1485343>.
- Tse, J. 2014. "Grounded Theologies." *Progress in Human Geography* 38 (2): 201–220. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/soass_research/3134.
- Vásquez, M. A. 2011. *More than Belief: A Materialist Theory of Religion*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
- Verkaaik, O., ed. 2013. *Religious Architecture: Anthropological Perspectives*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Amsterdam University Press.
- Wigley, E. 2018. "Unofficial Geographies of Religion and Spirituality as Postsecular Spaces." In *The Routledge Handbook of Postsecularity*, edited by J. Beaumont, 371–382. London, UK: Routledge.
- Woods, O. 2012. "The Geographies of Religious Conversion." *Progress in Human Geography* 36 (4): 440–456. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/soass_research/2427.
- Woods, O. 2019. "Religious Urbanism in Singapore: Competition, Commercialism and Compromise in the Search for Space." *Social Compass* 66 (1): 24–34. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/soass_research/2703.
- Woods, O., and L. Kong. 2022. "Aestheticized Temples, Rationalized Affects: Sacred Modernities and the Micro-regulation of Hinduism in Singapore." *Journal of Cultural Geography* 39 (2): 182–200. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/soass_research/3575.
- Woods, O., and L. Kong. 2023. "The Demands of Displacement, the Micro-aggressions of Multiculturalism: Performing an Idea of "Indianness" in Singapore." *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 46 (1): 119–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2022.2059387>.
- Woods, O., and L. Kong. 2024. "The Irreducible Otherness Ofdesiand Desire in Singapore'sgurdwaras: Moral Boundary-Making in the Shadows of a Multicultural Society." *Ethnic and Racial Studies* 47 (6): 1258–1279. https://ink.library.smu.edu.sg/cis_research/127.
- Ye, J. 2017. "Managing Urban Diversity through Differential Inclusion in Singapore." *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space* 35 (6): 1033–1052. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263775817717988>.
- Zanfrini, L. 2024. *30° rapporto sulle migrazioni*. Fondazione ISMU.